

Oxo-Vanadium(IV) Complexes with some Nitrogen Donors

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There has been considerable interest in the co-ordination chemistry of oxo-vanadium (IV) during the last several years as reflected in the appearance of two review articles by Selbin¹. In continuation of our active interest in the fascinating complex chemistry of oxo-vanadium(IV),²⁻⁷ this note describes the synthesis and characterisation of few vanadyl complexes with some unusual organic ligands namely, α -nitroso- β -naphthylamine, β -nitroso- α -naphthylamine, α -amino- β -naphthol-4-sulphonic acid, α -nitroso- β -naphthol-4-sulphonic acid and ortho-aminophenol. Compounds of vanadium with α -nitroso- β -naphthol and β -nitroso- α -naphthol have been reported earlier³.

EXPERIMENTAL

Tetravalent vanadium was taken as B.D.H. vanadyl sulphate penta-hydrate ($\text{VOSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$). Methanol used was of E. Merck's G.R. variety. The electrolytic conductance measurements were performed with the help of a Philip's Conductivity Bridge and a dip type cell. The room temperature magnetic susceptibility was determined by a Gouy Balance with solid specimens using recrystallised $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ as the calibrant. Diamagnetic corrections for the atoms was computed from Pascal's constants⁸. Vanadium was estimated gravimetrically as V_2O_5 and nitrogen by semimicro Duma's combustion technique.

1. *Bis*(α -nitroso- β -naphthylamine) Oxo-vanadium(IV): α -Nitroso- β -naphthylamine (0.70 g) was dissolved in ethanol (20 ml) and added gradually with stirring to a solution of vanadyl sulphate (0.50 g) in water (6-7 ml). The pH of the solution was then raised to 4-4.5 by dilute ammonium hydroxide when a voluminous cinnamon black precipitate was thrown down. This was filtered, washed with water followed by ethanol and dried in a desiccator over CaCl_2 . Found: V, 12.5; N, 13.7, magnetic moment=1.75 B.M. Reqd. for $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_8\text{N}_2\text{O})_2]$, V, 12.4; N, 13.6%.

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1. J. Selbin, *Chem. Revs.*, 1965, **65**, 153; *Coord. Chem. Revs.*, 1966, **1**, 293.
2. R. L. Dutta, A. Syamal and S. Ghosh, *This Journal*, 1966, **43**, 526.
3. R. L. Dutta and A. Syamal, *This Journal*, 1967, **44**, 381.
4. A. Syamal, *This Journal*, 1967, **44**, 656.
5. A. Syamal, D. Phil. Thesis, Burdwan University, 1966.
6. R. L. Dutta *et al.*, *This Journal*, 1961, **38**, 1001; 1962, **39**, 871, 860; 1963, **40**, 53, 67, 857; 1964, **41**, 62, 546; 1967, **44**, 273, 290, 296, 306, 369, 377, 738, 811; *Science & Culture*, 1960, **26**, 139; 1964, **30**, 551; *Chem. Ind. (London)*, 1961, 78; *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1966, **28**, 247.
7. R. L. Dutta, G. P. Sengupta, and A. Syamal, (to be published)
8. P. W. Selwood, "Magnetochemistry" Interscience Publishers, Inc., New York, 1956, p-92.

2. *Bis* (β -nitroso- α -naphthylamine) *Oxo-vanadium*(IV) (Cinnamon black) was prepared by following a similar procedure as for the α -nitroso- β naphthylamine derivative. Found: V, 12.6; N, 13.4, magnetic moment=1.78 B.M. Reqd. for $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_8\text{N}_2\text{O})_2]$, V, 12.4; N, 13.6%.

3. *Bis* (α -amino- β -naphthol-4-sulphonic acid) *Oxo-vanadium*(IV): α -Amino- β -naphthol-4-sulphonic acid (0.48 g) was dissolved in hot ethanol (10 ml) and was treated with an aqueous solution of vanadyl sulphate (0.50 g in 7 ml). The solution was then agitated on a steam bath for a few minutes. The brown crystals separated on cooling were filtered, washed with water followed by cold aqueous ethanol and dried as usual. Found: V, 9.5; N, 5.0; conductivity in methanol=5 mhos; magnetic moment=1.74 B.M. Reqd. for $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_8\text{NO}_4\text{S})_2]$, V, 9.3; N, 5.1%.

4. *Bis* (α -nitroso- β naphthol-4-sulphonic acid) *Oxo-vanadium*(IV) (Black) was prepared similarly as the compound 3. Found: V, 9.0; N, 5.0; conductivity in methanol=7 mhos; magnetic moment=1.74 B.M. Reqd. for $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_6\text{O}_6\text{NS})_2]$, V, 8.9; N, 4.9%.

5. *Bis*(ortho-aminophenol) *Oxo-vanadium*(IV): An aqueous acetonetic solution of ortho-aminophenol(0.44 g) was added to an aqueous solution of vanadyl sulphate (0.50 g in 7 ml.). The pH of the mixture was adjusted to 5 with dilute ammonium hydroxide. The separated dark brown crystals were filtered and washed repeatedly with acetone and dried in a desiccator. Found: V, 17.7; N, 9.6; magnetic moment=1.80 B.M. Reqd. for $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_6\text{NO})_2]$, V, 18.0; N, 9.8%.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The complexes were prepared under strictly controlled conditions and on the basis of percentages of metal and nitrogen, the general molecular formula of the complexes may be represented as $[\text{VO R}_2]$ (where $\text{RH} = \alpha$ -nitroso- β -naphthylamine etc.) showing that two molecules of bidentate ligands are coordinated to oxo-vanadium. The complexes are inert as they do not decompose, even if heated at 120° for hours. The compounds appear to be non-electrolytes and suffer no appreciable ionisation in aqueous medium as evident from their insolubility in water and solubility in alcohol. However, the poor solubility of the compounds in common organic solvents did not permit any evaluation of electronic absorption spectra and molecular complexity. All the complexes are paramagnetic and the value of the magnetic moment (1.7-1.8 B.M.) corresponds to a single spin of electron as expected for $3d^1$ system¹⁻⁶ The probable general structure may be represented as:

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